

54th Days of Preventive Medicine

International Congress

27-30. September 2022.

Niš, Serbia

BOOK OF ABSTRACT

Public Health Institute Niš

Faculty of Medicine,
University of Niš

Serbian Medical Society

Niš, 2022.

*122 years of Public Health Protection in Serbia
from regular preventive activities
to great challenges in COVID-19 pandemic time*

*122 године заштите јавног здравља у Србији
од редовних превентивних активности
до великих изазова у време пандемије COVID-19*

**PUBLIC HEALTH INSTITUTE NIŠ
FACULTY OF MEDICINE, UNIVERSITY OF NIŠ
SERBIAN MEDICAL SOCIETY, NIŠ**

**54TH DAYS OF PREVENTIVE MEDICINE
INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS**

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MAIN TOPICS

- **Environment and health**
- **Nutrition and health**
- **Microbiology today**
- **Current parasitosis**
- **Theoretical and practical problems of communicable diseases**
- **Theoretical and practical problems of non-communicable diseases**
- **Health promotion – challenges and solutions**
- **Preventive aspect of healthcare organization**
- **Application of information and communication tools in the health care system**

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9. DIETARY SUPPLEMENTS FOR IMMUNE FUNCTION INTENDED FOR USE IN PEDIATRIC POPULATION AVAILABLE AT THE SERBIAN MARKET

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Objectives: The aim of this research was to identify dietary supplements (DS) for immune function intended for use among children available at the Serbian market and assess their characteristics. **Methods:** DS available on the market were identified using the National dietary products' database and online pharmacies' inventories. Data on specific DS were obtained from their labels. **Results:** A total of 33 DS for immune function of children have been identified (67% in the form of syrups and chewable tablets). Majority of DS (91%) had more than one active ingredients, namely vitamins, minerals and/or botanicals. The most common active ingredients were vitamin C (76%), zinc (51%), vitamin D (47%), vitamin B₆ (45%) and vitamin A (45%). Botanicals were present in 67% of DS and included dog rose, elderberry, echinacea, cranberry and ganoderma extracts. In 80% of the cases, health claims made on DS declarations were not compliant with the national rulebook. Excipients with the potential for causing adverse effects were present in 67% of DS. **Conclusion:** The versatility of DS for children's immune function makes it hard for parents/caregivers to choose between them properly. Therefore, healthcare professionals should be considered essential links between DS and DS users.

Keywords: dietary supplements; immune function; children